

Clinician Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practice Survey

Site information	
1. Hospital code	__ __ - __ __ __ (country code – hospital ID)
Bacterial culture practices	
2. Does this hospital have a guideline for culture specimen collection guideline (i.e. recommendation on when/from which patient to take a specimen)?	
<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Don't know <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to answer	
3. As part of the diagnostic work up in patients with suspected bacterial infections, in what proportion of patients do you request collection of specimens for microbiology testing?	
<input type="radio"/> All patients (>95% of patients) <input type="radio"/> Most patients (50-95% of patients) <input type="radio"/> Some patients (5-50% of patients) <input type="radio"/> Few patients (<5% of patients) <input type="radio"/> None <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to answer	
4. Do you take blood cultures in patients starting parenteral antibiotic treatment?	
<input type="radio"/> Always (>95% of the times) <input type="radio"/> Often (50-95% of the times) <input type="radio"/> Sometimes (5-50% of the times) <input type="radio"/> Rarely (<5% of the time) <input type="radio"/> Never (None) <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to answer	
5. Do you take blood cultures in patients with suspected sepsis/bloodstream infection?	
<input type="radio"/> Always (>95% of the times) <input type="radio"/> Often (50-95% of the times) <input type="radio"/> Sometimes (5-50% of the times) <input type="radio"/> Rarely (<5% of the time) <input type="radio"/> Never (None) <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to answer	
6. Do you take sputum cultures in patients with suspected bacterial pneumonia?	
<input type="radio"/> Always (>95% of the times) <input type="radio"/> Often (50-95% of the times) <input type="radio"/> Sometimes (5-50% of the times) <input type="radio"/> Rarely (<5% of the time) <input type="radio"/> Never (None) <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to answer	
7. Do you take urine cultures in patients with suspected urinary tract infection?	
<input type="radio"/> Always (>95% of the times) <input type="radio"/> Often (50-95% of the times) <input type="radio"/> Sometimes (5-50% of the times) <input type="radio"/> Rarely (<5% of the time) <input type="radio"/> Never (None) <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to answer	
8. What are reason(s) for you to order blood culture sampling? (you can select more than one answer)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Patients presenting with chills <input type="checkbox"/> Leucocytosis <input type="checkbox"/> Patients can afford the cost of blood culture <input type="checkbox"/> Patients presenting with sepsis or septic shock <input type="checkbox"/> Neutropenia <input type="checkbox"/> Health insurance requirement <input type="checkbox"/> Patients presenting with infection and having underlying diseases <input type="checkbox"/> Left shift in blood count <input type="checkbox"/> Follow hospital guideline <input type="checkbox"/> Patients starting parenteral antibiotic treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Elevated CRP or procalcitonin <input type="checkbox"/> Other: <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to answer	

Clinician Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practice Survey

9. In this hospital, blood cultures are useless because results often arrive too late to be useful for making decisions about antibiotic treatment

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided/Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 Prefer not to answer

10. In this hospital, blood cultures are useless because they only rarely give a causative organism and actionable antibiotic susceptibility results

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided/Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 Prefer not to answer

11. In this hospital, blood cultures are useless because most patients have already received empirical antibiotics upon admission

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided/Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 Prefer not to answer

12. In this hospital, culture results are efficiently communicated to the treating clinician

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided/Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 Prefer not to answer

13. In this hospital, in general how long does it take to get a positive blood culture result from the microbiology laboratory?

- 1-3 days 4-7 days >7 days Often do not get the result
 Prefer not to answer

14. This hospital publishes a regular (e.g. yearly) AMR surveillance report summarising the resistance patterns for common pathogens

- Yes No Don't know
 Prefer not to answer

Your views on antimicrobial resistance (AMR), diagnostic stewardship and AMR surveillance

15. AMR is a problem in this country

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided/Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 Prefer not to answer

16. AMR is a problem in this hospital

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided/Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 Prefer not to answer

17. The optimal timing to collect patient specimens for blood culture is

- Before starting antibiotics After starting antibiotics Does not matter when
 Prefer not to answer

Clinician Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practice Survey

18. Blood cultures are useful in detecting antimicrobial-resistant bacterial infections

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided/Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 Prefer not to answer

19. Blood cultures are helpful in targeting antibiotic therapy

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided/Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 Prefer not to answer

20. Blood cultures can reduce unnecessary use of antibiotics

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided/Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 Prefer not to answer

21. Blood cultures can improve patient management

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided/Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 Prefer not to answer

22. Cumulative hospital antimicrobial resistance data (i.e. hospital antibiogram) can be used for developing local antibiotic treatment guidelines

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided/Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 Prefer not to answer

23. Laboratory-based AMR surveillance is an important component of the efforts to tackle the AMR problem

(Laboratory-based AMR surveillance means systematic collection of microbiology laboratory data to estimate the burden of AMR, detect trends, and inform treatment guidelines)

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided/Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 Prefer not to answer

24. Data from this hospital should be shared with the Ministry of Health for national AMR surveillance

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided/Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 Prefer not to answer

Background information

25. What is your current grade or position?

- Intern Resident Senior doctor / specialist / consultant General practitioner Other
 Prefer not to answer

26. How long have you worked as a medical doctor?

- <1 year 1-5 years 6-10 years >10 years
 Prefer not to answer

Clinician Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practice Survey

27. What is your primary work unit / department in this hospital?

- | | | |
|--|--|------------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Internal medicine | <input type="radio"/> Neonatology | <input type="radio"/> Orthopaedics |
| <input type="radio"/> Surgery | <input type="radio"/> Intensive Care | <input type="radio"/> Other |
| <input type="radio"/> Emergency Dept | <input type="radio"/> Obstetrics/Gynaecology | <input type="radio"/> Mixed |
| <input type="radio"/> Paediatrics | <input type="radio"/> Pulmonology | |
| <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to answer | | |

28. During the past year, have you received training/teaching or attended seminars/courses on antimicrobial prescribing, resistance and/or stewardship?

- | | | |
|--|--------------------------|----------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Yes | <input type="radio"/> No | <input type="radio"/> Don't know |
| <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to answer | | |

Enrolment			
Hospital code (country code – hospital ID)	_ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _		
Participant details			
Date of enrolment (dd-mmm-yyyy)	_ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _		
Patient hospital ID (this ID must be present in the hospital microbiology lab database / LIMS)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _		
ACORN ID	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _		
Date of birth (dd-mmm-yyyy)	_ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _		
Age (if DOB unknown)	_ _ Years	_ _ Months	_ _ Days
Gender	<input type="checkbox"/> Female	<input type="checkbox"/> Male	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown	
Date of admission (dd-mmm-yyyy)	_ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _		
Transfer from another hospital	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Transfer from another facility (e.g. long-term care facility)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Date of hospitalisation (if transfer from another facility)	_ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _		
Admission type	<input type="checkbox"/> Emergency	<input type="checkbox"/> Elective	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Primary admission reason	<input type="checkbox"/> Infectious disease	<input type="checkbox"/> Orthopaedic (non-trauma)	<input type="checkbox"/> Cardiovascular
	<input type="checkbox"/> Endocrine / Metabolic	<input type="checkbox"/> Gastrointestinal	<input type="checkbox"/> Renal
	<input type="checkbox"/> Genitourinary	<input type="checkbox"/> Haematological	<input type="checkbox"/> Neurological
	<input type="checkbox"/> Pulmonary	<input type="checkbox"/> Trauma	<input type="checkbox"/> Gynaecological
	<input type="checkbox"/> Connective tissue disease / Rheumatologic	<input type="checkbox"/> Dermatological	<input type="checkbox"/> Oncologic
	<input type="checkbox"/> Undetermined		
Comorbidities			
	<input type="checkbox"/> Congestive heart failure	<input type="checkbox"/> Chronic pulmonary disease	<input type="checkbox"/> Mild liver disease
	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate or severe liver disease	<input type="checkbox"/> Connective tissue / rheumatologic disease	<input type="checkbox"/> Peptic ulcer
	<input type="checkbox"/> Diabetes	<input type="checkbox"/> Diabetes with end organ damage	<input type="checkbox"/> Hemi- or paraplegia
	<input type="checkbox"/> Renal disease	<input type="checkbox"/> Cancer/leukaemia	<input type="checkbox"/> Metastatic solid tumour

Patient Case Record Form F01 – Enrolment

ACORN ID: _____

<input type="checkbox"/> AIDS	<input type="checkbox"/> Dementia	<input type="checkbox"/> Malaria
<input type="checkbox"/> HIV on ART	<input type="checkbox"/> HIV without ART	<input type="checkbox"/> Malnutrition
<input type="checkbox"/> Tuberculosis		

Recent healthcare exposure

Overnight hospitalisation in the 3 months (90 days) before admission	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Regular hospital contact (e.g. dialysis, cancer treatment in the 3 months (90 days before admission)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Surgery in the 3 months (90 days) before admission	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown

Completed by: _____

Completion date: _____

Infection episode			
Hospital code (country code – hospital ID)	_ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _		
ACORN ID	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _		
Date of admission (dd-mmm-yyyy)	_ _ - _ _ _ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _		
Date of episode enrolment (dd-mmm-yyyy)	_ _ - _ _ _ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _		
Patient age category	<input type="checkbox"/> Adult (≥18y)	<input type="checkbox"/> Child (1m – 17y)	<input type="checkbox"/> Neonate (<28d)
Surveillance category	<input type="checkbox"/> CAI	<input type="checkbox"/> HAI	
Date of symptom onset (HAI only) (dd-mmm-yyyy)	_ _ - _ _ _ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _		
Ward type	<input type="checkbox"/> Adult medical	<input type="checkbox"/> Paediatric medical	<input type="checkbox"/> Neonatal medical
	<input type="checkbox"/> Adult surgical	<input type="checkbox"/> Paediatric surgical	<input type="checkbox"/> Neonatal surgical
	<input type="checkbox"/> Adult ICU	<input type="checkbox"/> Paediatric ICU	<input type="checkbox"/> Neonatal ICU
	<input type="checkbox"/> Obstetrics / Gynaecology	<input type="checkbox"/> Haematology / Oncology	<input type="checkbox"/> Emergency department
Ward name	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _		
Clinically suspected infection (reason for IV antibiotic prescription) – definitions at bottom of page	<input type="checkbox"/> Central nervous system	<input type="checkbox"/> Cardiovascular system	<input type="checkbox"/> Eye
	<input type="checkbox"/> ENT / Upper respiratory tract	<input type="checkbox"/> Lower respiratory tract	<input type="checkbox"/> Pneumonia
	<input type="checkbox"/> Gastrointestinal	<input type="checkbox"/> Intra-abdominal	<input type="checkbox"/> Necrotising enterocolitis
	<input type="checkbox"/> Skin / Soft tissue	<input type="checkbox"/> Bone / Joint	<input type="checkbox"/> Surgical site
	<input type="checkbox"/> Urinary tract	<input type="checkbox"/> Genital	<input type="checkbox"/> Febrile neutropenia
	<input type="checkbox"/> Sepsis (source unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (diagnosis documented)	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown (not documented)
Severity score: qSOFA score (participant is ≥18 years) on day of admission (CAI) or symptom onset (HAI)			
Altered mentation (GCS <15)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Respiratory rate (≥22 /min)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Systolic blood pressure (<100 mmHg)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Abnormal core temperature (<36°C or > 38°C) [not part of qSOFA]	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown

Severity score: sepsis-6 features (participant is <18 years) on day of admission (CAI) or symptom onset (HAI) – definitions at bottom of page

Abnormal core temperature	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Inappropriate tachycardia	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Altered mental state	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Reduced peripheral perfusion or prolonged capillary refill time	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
If neonatal patient (<28 days), reduced level of activity	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
If neonatal patient (<28 days), feeding difficulty	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
If neonatal patient (<28 days), convulsions	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown

Medical devices / procedures (HAI only)

Medical devices present on the day of HAI symptom onset	<input type="checkbox"/> Peripheral IV catheter	<input type="checkbox"/> Central IV catheter	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Urinary catheter	<input type="checkbox"/> Intubation / Mechanical ventilation	
Admitted to ICU for more than 48 hours (2 days) since admission and day of HAI symptom onset	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Surgery since admission and day of HAI symptom onset	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown

Blood culture details

Blood culture collected within 24 hours of admission (CAI) or symptom onset (HAI)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Received ≥1 dose of a systemic antibiotic in the 24 hours before the blood culture collected	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown

Empiric antibiotic treatment

Systemic antibiotics prescribed on date of admission (CAI) or symptom onset (HAI)	<input type="checkbox"/> Amikacin	<input type="checkbox"/> Amoxicillin	<input type="checkbox"/> Amoxicillin-Clavulanate
	<input type="checkbox"/> Ampicillin	<input type="checkbox"/> Ampicillin-Sulbactam	<input type="checkbox"/> Azithromycin
	<input type="checkbox"/> Benzylpenicillin	<input type="checkbox"/> Cefepime	<input type="checkbox"/> Cefixime
	<input type="checkbox"/> Cefotaxime	<input type="checkbox"/> Ceftriaxone	<input type="checkbox"/> Ceftazidime
	<input type="checkbox"/> Cephalexin	<input type="checkbox"/> Ciprofloxacin	<input type="checkbox"/> Clarithromycin
	<input type="checkbox"/> Clindamycin	<input type="checkbox"/> Cloxacillin	<input type="checkbox"/> Co-trimoxazole
	<input type="checkbox"/> Daptomycin	<input type="checkbox"/> Doripenem	<input type="checkbox"/> Doxycycline
	<input type="checkbox"/> Ertapenem	<input type="checkbox"/> Erythromycin	<input type="checkbox"/> Gentamicin
	<input type="checkbox"/> Imipenem	<input type="checkbox"/> Levofloxacin	<input type="checkbox"/> Linezolid
	<input type="checkbox"/> Meropenem	<input type="checkbox"/> Metronidazole	<input type="checkbox"/> Moxifloxacin
	<input type="checkbox"/> Norfloxacin	<input type="checkbox"/> Ofloxacin	<input type="checkbox"/> Penicillin V

Patient Case Record Form F02 – Infection episode

ACORN ID: _____

Piperacillin-Tazobactam

Roxithromycin

Teicoplanin

Tetracycline

Tigecycline

Vancomycin

Unknown

Other, please specify _____

Completed by: _____

Completion date: _____

Definitions

Infection category	Examples
Central nervous system	Brain abscess, encephalitis, meningitis, myelitis, spinal abscess, ventriculitis
Cardiovascular system	Endocarditis, mediastinitis, myocarditis, pericarditis, vascular (arterial or venous) infection
Eye	Conjunctivitis, dacryocystitis, endophthalmitis, orbital cellulitis
ENT / Upper respiratory tract	Epiglottitis, mastoiditis, otitis media, retropharyngeal abscess, sinusitis, tonsillitis
Lower respiratory tract	Bronchitis, bronchiolitis, lung abscess, tracheitis, tracheobronchitis, without evidence of pneumonia
Pneumonia	Pneumonia
Gastrointestinal	Colitis, dysentery, gastroenteritis
Intra-abdominal	Appendicitis, cholangitis, cholecystitis, liver / spleen abscess, pancreatitis, peritonitis
Necrotising enterocolitis	Neonatal necrotising enterocolitis
Skin / Soft tissue	Abscess, bites, burn, cellulitis, infectious gangrene, lymphadenitis, lymphangitis, necrotising fasciitis, pyomyositis, ulcer
Bone / Joint	Disc space infection, osteomyelitis, septic arthritis / bursitis
Surgical site infection	Post-operative infection (<30 days / <90 days if implant in situ) involving the surgical incision or deeper tissues associated with the procedure
Urinary tract	Cystitis, pyelonephritis
Genital	Obstetric / gynaecologic infections (ovarian abscess, salpingitis / PID, endometritis, episiotomy infection), prostatitis, sexually transmitted infections
Febrile neutropenia	Febrile neutropenic episode (haematology-oncology)
Sepsis	Clinical sepsis (source unclear / WITHOUT obvious focus / not specified)
Other	Defined diagnosis but not included in the list
Unknown	Reason for antibiotic not documented

Paediatric severity definitions:	Abnormal core temperature	<36.0°C / >38.5°C tympanic OR <35.5°C / > 38.0°C axillary
	Inappropriate tachycardia	<1y: ≥160 /min 1-2y: ≥150 /min 3-4y: ≥140 /min 5y and above: ≥130 /min
	Altered mental state	GCS<15 OR Sleepiness, irritability, lethargy, floppiness
	Reduced peripheral perfusion or prolonged capillary refill time	Cold feet or hands OR ≥3 seconds

Patient Case Record Form F03 – Discharge

ACORN ID: _____

- | | | |
|---|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gastrointestinal | <input type="checkbox"/> Intra-abdominal | <input type="checkbox"/> Necrotising enterocolitis |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Skin / Soft tissue | <input type="checkbox"/> Bone / Joint | <input type="checkbox"/> Surgical site |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Urinary tract | <input type="checkbox"/> Genital | <input type="checkbox"/> Febrile neutropenia |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Melioidosis | <input type="checkbox"/> Typhoid | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other (diagnosis documented) | <input type="checkbox"/> Undefined (infection treated but no site / source of identified) | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown (not documented) | <input type="checkbox"/> Infection rejected (alternative diagnosis made) | |

Infection episode #4

Infection episode enrolment date (dd-mmm-yyyy)

|_|_|_|-|_|_|_|-|_|_|_|_|_|

- | | | | |
|-----------------------------------|--|---|--|
| Final infection episode diagnosis | <input type="checkbox"/> Central nervous system | <input type="checkbox"/> Cardiovascular system | <input type="checkbox"/> Eye |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> ENT / Upper respiratory tract | <input type="checkbox"/> Lower respiratory tract | <input type="checkbox"/> Pneumonia |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Gastrointestinal | <input type="checkbox"/> Intra-abdominal | <input type="checkbox"/> Necrotising enterocolitis |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Skin / Soft tissue | <input type="checkbox"/> Bone / Joint | <input type="checkbox"/> Surgical site |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Urinary tract | <input type="checkbox"/> Genital | <input type="checkbox"/> Febrile neutropenia |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Melioidosis | <input type="checkbox"/> Typhoid | |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Other (diagnosis documented) | <input type="checkbox"/> Undefined (infection treated but no site / source of identified) | |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown (not documented) | <input type="checkbox"/> Infection rejected (alternative diagnosis made) | |

Infection episode #5

Infection episode enrolment date (dd-mmm-yyyy)

|_|_|_|-|_|_|_|-|_|_|_|_|_|

- | | | | |
|-----------------------------------|--|---|--|
| Final infection episode diagnosis | <input type="checkbox"/> Central nervous system | <input type="checkbox"/> Cardiovascular system | <input type="checkbox"/> Eye |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> ENT / Upper respiratory tract | <input type="checkbox"/> Lower respiratory tract | <input type="checkbox"/> Pneumonia |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Gastrointestinal | <input type="checkbox"/> Intra-abdominal | <input type="checkbox"/> Necrotising enterocolitis |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Skin / Soft tissue | <input type="checkbox"/> Bone / Joint | <input type="checkbox"/> Surgical site |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Urinary tract | <input type="checkbox"/> Genital | <input type="checkbox"/> Febrile neutropenia |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Melioidosis | <input type="checkbox"/> Typhoid | |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Other (diagnosis documented) | <input type="checkbox"/> Undefined (infection treated but no site / source of identified) | |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown (not documented) | <input type="checkbox"/> Infection rejected (alternative diagnosis made) | |

Discharge details

Discharge status

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Alive | <input type="checkbox"/> Dead |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Left against medical advice | <input type="checkbox"/> Moribund: discharged to die at home |

Discharge to

- | | | |
|----------------------------------|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Home | <input type="checkbox"/> Long-term care facility | <input type="checkbox"/> Other hospital |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown | <input type="checkbox"/> NA (if death) | |

Patient Case Record Form F03 – Discharge

ACORN ID: _____

Date of discharge (dd-mmm-yyyy)	_ _ _ - _ _ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _
Total number of days on ICU during admission	_ _ _ _

Completed by: _____

Completion date: _____

Day 28 review [†]	
Hospital code (country code – hospital ID)	_ _ _ - _ _ _ _
ACORN ID	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _
Date of admission (dd-mmm-yyyy)	_ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _
Date of 28-day review (dd-mmm-yyyy)	_ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _
Status at 28-day review	<input type="checkbox"/> Alive – fully recovered <input type="checkbox"/> Dead <input type="checkbox"/> Unable to contact <input type="checkbox"/> Alive – not back to normal activities
Date of death (if post-discharge)	_ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _

[†]One day 28 review per admission (taken as 28 days from the final infection episode enrolment date)

Completed by: _____

Completion date: _____

Pitt BSI score

Patient observations on the date of collection for the positive blood culture (or up to 48 hours before if not available):

Temperature (°C) [most extreme value]	_ _ _ . _ _	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown	
Respiratory rate (/min) [highest value]	_ _ _ _	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown	
Heart rate (/min) [highest value]	_ _ _ _	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown	
Systolic BP (mmHg) [lowest value]	_ _ _ _	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown	
Mental status [lowest value]	<input type="checkbox"/> Alert	<input type="checkbox"/> Disoriented	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Stuporous	<input type="checkbox"/> Comatose	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Acute hypotensive event (drop in systolic BP >30mmHg and diastolic BP >20mmHg)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown

In the 48 hours leading up to the date of collection for the positive blood culture, did any of the following occur:

Intravenous vasopressor agents required	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Mechanical ventilation needed	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Cardiac arrest	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown

Antibiotic treatment details – include both empiric and targeted treatment

Drug name	Start date (dd-mmm-yyyy)	End date (dd-mmm-yyyy)	Route (oral / intravenous / other)

BSI details

Was BSI primary or secondary	<input type="checkbox"/> Primary (unknown origin / central line)	<input type="checkbox"/> Secondary (defined infection focus)	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
	<input type="checkbox"/> Skin / Soft tissue	<input type="checkbox"/> Pulmonary	<input type="checkbox"/> Digestive tract
If secondary, what was the likely source	<input type="checkbox"/> Urinary tract	<input type="checkbox"/> Surgical site	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify _____		

If *S. aureus*, was it a complicated BSI?

Presence of implanted prosthesis	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
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Patient Case Record Form F05 – BSI episode

ACORN ID: _____

Duration of BSI >2 days Yes

No

Unknown

BSI-related fever >3 days Yes

No

Unknown

Completed by: _____

Completion date: _____

Hospital Acquired Infection Point Prevalence Survey Ward Case Record Form (F06)

Hospital Details	
Hospital code (country code – hospital ID)	_ _ - _ _ _ _ _
Survey date	
Date of survey (dd-mmm-yyyy)	_ _ - _ _ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _
Ward details	
Ward type	<input type="checkbox"/> Adult medical <input type="checkbox"/> Paediatric medical <input type="checkbox"/> Neonatal medical <input type="checkbox"/> Adult surgical <input type="checkbox"/> Paediatric surgical <input type="checkbox"/> Neonatal surgical <input type="checkbox"/> Adult ICU <input type="checkbox"/> Paediatric ICU <input type="checkbox"/> Neonatal ICU <input type="checkbox"/> Obstetrics / Gynaecology <input type="checkbox"/> Haematology / Oncology <input type="checkbox"/> Emergency department
	Ward name
	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes* <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown *patients from multiple services / specialties housed on the ward
	Total number of beds
Total number of patients	_ _ _ _ (resident in a bed at 8am on the day of the survey)
Number of medical patients	_ _ _ _
Number of surgical patients	_ _ _ _
Number of ICU patients	_ _ _ _

Completed by: _____

Completion date: _____

ACORN_o

Site Assessment Form

1. Hospital details			
Hospital name			
Hospital code <small>(country code – hospital ID)</small>	_ _ _ _ - _ _ _ _ _		
Country			
City / Town			
Year hospital opened			
Profile <small>(select all that apply, one from the left column and, if appropriate, one from the right column)</small>	<input type="checkbox"/> General hospital	<input type="checkbox"/> Paediatric only	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Specialty hospital	<input type="checkbox"/> Adult only	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other		
	Details:		
Level of care <small>(select all that apply)</small>	<input type="checkbox"/> Primary	<input type="checkbox"/> Secondary	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Tertiary	<input type="checkbox"/> National	
What important specialties are available in the hospital <small>(select all that apply)</small>	<input type="checkbox"/> Solid organ transplantation	<input type="checkbox"/> Obstetrics unit	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Bone marrow transplantation	<input type="checkbox"/> Clinical haematology (without transplantation)	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Burns unit	<input type="checkbox"/> Oncology	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Neonatal unit	<input type="checkbox"/> Others	
Details:			
Ownership <small>(select all that apply)</small>	<input type="checkbox"/> Government / Public	<input type="checkbox"/> Private, for profit	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Private, not for profit (Non-governmental / Charity)	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other		
Details:			

ACORN_o

Site Assessment Form

2. Hospital data for most recent complete year			
Year		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Total admissions		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Community admissions		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Transfers in		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Patients		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Beds (all)		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Beds (acute only)*		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
ICU beds		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Patient days		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Doctors (qualified, full FTE)		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Nurses (qualified, full FTE)		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown

*Exclude wards such as long-term care / rehabilitation / psychiatry

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Site Assessment Form

3. Are individual patient files handwritten or electronic?

<input type="checkbox"/> Handwritten	<input type="checkbox"/> Electronic	<input type="checkbox"/> Both (partly written and partly electronic)
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4. Does the hospital have an electronic billing and/or patient record system?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
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If yes, do these systems capture the following details?

Patient Name	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Address	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Date of admission	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Transfer status	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Diagnosis	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
ICD10 code(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Microbiology results	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Antibiotic treatment	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Date of discharge	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Discharge status	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown

5. Does the hospital advocate the use of specific guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of infections?

Sepsis / Suspected bloodstream infection	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/> Local guideline (hospital / department) <input type="checkbox"/> National guideline <input type="checkbox"/> International guideline Detail:
Pneumonia	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/> Local guideline (hospital / department) <input type="checkbox"/> National guideline <input type="checkbox"/> International guideline Detail:
Meningitis	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/> Local guideline (hospital / department) <input type="checkbox"/> National guideline <input type="checkbox"/> International guideline Detail:
Skin and soft tissue infections	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/> Local guideline (hospital / department) <input type="checkbox"/> National guideline <input type="checkbox"/> International guideline Detail:
Urinary tract infections	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/> Local guideline (hospital / department) <input type="checkbox"/> National guideline <input type="checkbox"/> International guideline Detail:
Other infections	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/> Local guideline (hospital / department) <input type="checkbox"/> National guideline <input type="checkbox"/> International guideline Detail:

6. How are the costs covered for diagnostic procedures for infections?

	Patient pays	National insurance pays	Number of tests covered	Other	Detail
Blood culture	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Sputum culture	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
BAL and culture	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Urine culture	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Lumbar puncture & CSF analysis (microscopy / protein + glucose)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
CSF culture	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Culture of other specimens (e.g. wound swab)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Chest x-ray	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Abdominal ultrasound	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
CT scan	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Complete blood count	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Blood urea nitrogen	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
C-reactive protein (CRP) or Procalcitonin (PCT)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	

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Site Assessment Form

7. Data for wards selected for ACORN surveillance (for the same year as Q2, i.e. the most recent complete year)

Summary data (enter total numbers or "NA" if not available)

Ward name / Abbreviation (e.g. in-patient ward 1 / IPD1)	Admissions	Beds	Patient days	Doctors	Nurses

1. Hospital details	
Hospital name	
Hospital code (country code – hospital ID)	_ _ _ - _ _ _ _

2. Annual hospital summary data			
Year		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Total admissions		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Community admissions		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Transfers in		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Patients		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Beds (all)		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Beds (acute only)*		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
ICU beds		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Patient days		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Doctors (qualified, full FTE)		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown
Nurses (qualified, full FTE)		<input type="checkbox"/>	Unknown

*Exclude wards such as long-term care / rehabilitation / psychiatry

ACORN Diagnostic Stewardship Checklist

Site details	
Site name	
Site code	

Existing clinical diagnostic stewardship items / activities			
Item	Yes	No	Details
Clinical case definitions for bacterial culture	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Sepsis / Suspected bloodstream infection	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Pneumonia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Meningitis	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Skin and soft tissue infections	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Urinary tract infection	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Other infections	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Microbiology specimen request form	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Technical guideline or SOP for how to collect specimens	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Specimen transport procedures formally defined	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Infectious disease / microbiology consult service	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Availability of infection biomarkers (c-reactive protein [CRP] and/or procalcitonin [PCT])	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	